

Metrological Characterization of EMI Receivers

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Abstract—This paper compares different hardware architectures of electromagnetic interference (EMI) receivers with respect to their calibration in a metrology laboratory. Basic tests for checking the receivers' compliance with the CISPR 16-1-1:2019 standard are described and practical aspects of their performance are presented. It is shown that testing of time-domain EMI receivers popular in many EMC testing areas (e.g., pre-compliance testing) for their conformity with the standard in a metrology laboratory is currently more time-consuming and not properly supported by the standard compared to traditional swept-frequency systems.

Index Terms—calibration, CISPR 16-1-1, electromagnetic compatibility, electromagnetic interference (EMI), measuring receiver

I. INTRODUCTION

Measuring receivers are used for the measurement of radio disturbance in the frequency range typically 9 kHz to 18 GHz. Traditionally such receivers are either electromagnetic interference (EMI) receivers or spectrum analyzers with the quasi-peak (QP) detector [1] working on the heterodyne principle. The advantages of Fourier transform-based receivers operating in the time domain have been highlighted for many electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) applications [2]. Using a time-domain (TD) EMI measurement system, the measurement time can be reduced by several orders of magnitude. The specifications of EMI receivers are given in the international standard IEC/CISPR 16-1-1 [3]. Metrological characterization of EMI receivers is a requirement of the international standard IEC/ISO 17025:2017 [4] for calibration and testing laboratories and the Annex K of standard [3]. This paper discusses certain practical aspects of the calibration of EMI receivers from the metrological point of view and the calibration of the equipment needed for EMI receivers calibration. It will be shown that the current standard [3] does not fully reflect the fast progress in hardware architectures of modern TD EMI receivers and most test methods are tailored to heterodyne frequency-swept systems.

II. EMI RECEIVER ARCHITECTURES

The frequency range of EMI receivers is usually 9 kHz to 1 GHz (CISPR bands A/B/C/D) or up to 18 GHz (CISPR band E). The most used receiver architectures are briefly described below.

A. Heterodyne Frequency-swept EMI Receivers

The heterodyne approach is well-proven and provides exceptional performance. The implementation is to mix to an intermediate frequency (IF) using a swept local oscillator (LO). The IF is chosen at a high enough frequency to allow practical filters in the operating band to provide good image rejection and LO isolation. It is also common to add a mixing stage to lower the frequency where very high dynamic range analog to digital (A/D) converters are available. It can be divided into four parts: (i) preselection stage, (ii) mixer, (iii) intermediate frequency bandpass filter and amplifier stage, and (iv) detector stage, as shown in Fig. 1. The IF is rectified to produce a video voltage representing the signal level versus time. This video voltage is sent to the detector circuits. The detectors deliver standard-compliant, weighted measurement results at their outputs: the peak value, average value, quasi-peak value, etc. Nowadays, many analogue components are replaced by their digital representation. This is made possible with the fast Fourier transform (FFT) and short-time Fourier transform (STFT) functions. An extensive description of heterodyne receivers is given e.g. in [5]. The use of heterodyne receivers for EMC compliance testing is slow and there is also some dead time between sweeps while the system is measuring, processing the data, and displaying the results. This delay can miss some pulsating or intermittent frequency captures.

Fig. 1. Principle of a heterodyne receiver.

B. Real-time Spectrum Analyzers with QP Option

The working principle of real-time spectrum analyzers is similar to the heterodyne principle with the difference that it contains an A/D converter after the IF filter instead of the envelope detector, i.e. the analogue signal processing is replaced by the digital one. Using digital signal processing, the spectrum of the input signal is calculated. Moreover, it

digitizes the signal mixed onto the intermediate frequency before the signal is limited to the chosen IF bandwidth. The available frequency span corresponds to the IF bandwidth, and to obtain the full frequency spectrum, many acquisitions have to be taken with overlapping frequency windows. In this way, zero dead time is achieved so that 100 % of the signal is acquired and no intermittent pulses are missed. When measuring a frequency spectrum e.g. 9 kHz to 1 GHz, the only option is to tune the receive frequency in steps smaller than the measurement bandwidth and compile the spectrum from a series of individually conducted measurements, see e.g. [6]. The typical hardware architecture of a real-time spectrum analyzer is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Typical hardware architecture of a real-time spectrum analyzer.

C. Time-domain EMI receivers

The TD EMI receivers work on the principle of a fast A/D converter which is directly at the receiver's input (sometimes after an attenuator or filter) so that no local oscillator is needed and the whole spectrum of the input signal is computed at once. There exist several architectures of TD EMI receivers, such as multiresolution systems for enhancing dynamic range based on field programmable gate arrays (FPGA) [7], commercial systems based on multichannel oscilloscopes digitizing the signal without frequency conversion to IF (see, e.g., [8], [9] for frequencies below 1 GHz). A system capable of measuring up to 18 GHz was presented e.g. in [10], where a multi-stage broadband down-converter using a local oscillator was used to convert the input signal into a lower frequency band and then an A/D converter with a sampling rate of 2.6 GSa/s was used. There are also high-end oscilloscopes operating in real-time with bandwidths exceeding 18 GHz; however, the equivalent number of bits (ENOB) is usually 5-7, which leads to very poor vertical resolution compared to 12-bit multichannel oscilloscopes with bandwidths below 1 GHz, moreover, the amount of data to be processed is huge. The TD receivers implemented with oscilloscopes are very popular for pre-compliance and in-situ testing. Still, the oscilloscope approach might not be suitable for tests with extremely low emissions limits, like in some automotive or aerospace applications. Advanced digital signal processing is used, such as short-time FFT and periodogram analysis together with the digital implementation of detectors (peak, average, RMS, quasi-peak), see e.g. [11], [12]. The typical hardware architecture of a TD EMI receiver is shown in Fig. 3.

III. CALIBRATION OF EMI RECEIVERS

The traditional way of checking the compliance of receivers with the pulse response requirements of the

Fig. 3. Typical hardware architecture of a TD EMI receiver.

standard [3] is using a calibrated pulse generator [13], [14]. With the growing popularity of TD EMI receivers (often without input preselection filters), it has been debated for a long how to satisfy their conformance with the CISPR 16-1-1 requirements (quasi-peak detector) without the use of pulse generators that may potentially be harmful to the receiver input. To generate spectrum amplitudes specified in [3], narrow pulses with amplitudes in order of tens or hundreds of volts are needed which may destroy the receiver's A/D converter. One option is to use an RF sine-wave signal modulated with periodic rectangular pulses (also used to verify the AVG and RMS detectors). The spectrum flatness and response to pulses can also be fulfilled by other waveforms, such as trapezoidal waveform numerically synthesized by an arbitrary waveform generator [15] or a broadband multi-sine signal [1], however, this approach is only applicable to CISPR bands A/B, because typical arbitrary waveform generators are limited by the output signal amplitude. The CISPR bands C/D would again require amplitudes in order of tens to hundreds of volts (both for the synthesized trapezoidal and multisine waveforms). Using alternative waveforms with possibly lower energy (i.e. lower required spectrum amplitude) is technically sound as there are no natural or artificial disturbance sources with such high energy measured by EMI receivers in typical EMC testing scenarios. To date, using alternative waveforms with lower energy is not covered by CISPR 16-1-1 [3].

The following text will discuss methods for calibration of EMI receivers and specific differences for particular hardware architectures. According to Annex K of [3], the demonstration of compliance of measuring receivers with the standard can be provided through the manufacturer's calibration process or using procedures and measuring equipment defined in the standard. It is worth mentioning that the current standardized calibration procedure is tailored to the heterodyne receiver architecture, and it does not consider some specific problems of TD EMI receivers. The manufacturer's calibration process is usually more extensive as it validates not only functions related to disturbance measurements but also checks the instrument's general performance.

A list of the typical EMI receiver's parameters that are calibrated includes the input impedance; sine-wave voltage level tolerance; overall pass-band selectivity; bandwidth; frequency tuning accuracy; intermediate frequency rejection ratio; image frequency rejection ratio; other spurious responses (e.g., 3rd order intercept point); limitation of

intermodulation effects; limitations of receiver noise and internally-generated spurious signals; limitation of radio-frequency emissions from the measuring receiver and response to pulses of the weighting detectors.

Due to the various architectures of EMI receivers, there are four core parameters that each EMI receiver should satisfy to be compliant with [3] (black box approach). These parameters are discussed in the following subsections separately.

A. Sine-wave Voltage Level Tolerance

For heterodyne EMI receivers or real-time FFT spectrum analyzers, one only needs a CW generator with a calibrated power meter to check the level of accuracy at selected frequencies. These receivers usually have a very low input reflection coefficient (typically <0.05 in linear scale up to 18 GHz) and thus the measurement uncertainty due to impedance matching is given by

$$M_{dB} = 20 \log |1 \pm \Gamma_g \Gamma_{rec}|, \quad (1)$$

where Γ_g is the reflection coefficient of the signal source (usually effective source match of a resistive power divider) and Γ_{rec} is the input reflection coefficient of the EMI receiver in linear scale. Time-domain EMI receivers based on an oscilloscope with 50Ω input usually have a much worse input reflection coefficient at frequencies >500 MHz (only seldom specified by manufacturers, values measured using a vector network analyzer (VNA) are typically up to 0.3 in linear scale without an input attenuator or preamplifier, which is the upper limit of [3] in the band up to 1 GHz) resulting in higher mismatch uncertainty and thus worse sine level measurement accuracy. In some cases, TD EMI receivers based on an oscilloscope only have $1 \text{ M}\Omega$ input impedance (typically parallel with capacitance 6 pF to 14 pF), whereas the standard [3] assumes an EMI receiver to have 50Ω input impedance. In such cases, quality feed-through 50Ω load must be used. For TD EMI receivers which measure the whole spectrum at once, it was proposed to use artificially synthesized multi-sine signal [1]. Manufacturers of EMI receivers usually recommend using one power level in the whole frequency range of a particular CISPR band (e.g. $70 \text{ dB}(\mu\text{V})$). Authors of [1] used the CISPR 32 class B emission limit, i.e. a target level mask instead of a constant value, because this mask is important for determining compliance with CISPR standards. The response of all detectors to the sine wave should be the same.

B. Frequency Tuning Accuracy

For heterodyne EMI receivers or real-time FFT spectrum analyzers, a calibrated frequency counter is needed for measurement of the 10 MHz reference frequency output (if present) or for measurement of the frequency of the signal at the receiver input and comparison with the reading of the receiver. Heterodyne EMI receivers or real-time FFT analyzers use a local oscillator (synthesizer) with very fine frequency resolution thus it is no problem to achieve

frequency steps in order of fractions of Hertz. On the other hand, the frequency resolution of TD EMI receivers is dependent on the time epoch which is captured. The frequency resolution is then given as $\Delta f = 1/(NT_s)$, where N is the number of waveform samples and T_s is the sampling period (reciprocal sampling rate f_s). The samplers in TD EMI receivers usually allow discrete values of sampling rates and the number of samples is limited due to memory. For instance, capturing 1s of input waveform means a frequency resolution of 1 Hz after conversion of the input samples into the frequency domain. With the sampling rate of 62.5 MSa/s (CISPR band B), it corresponds to 62.5 million samples which may be beyond the memory limitation of cheap oscilloscopes or FPGA solutions. For that reason, a much shorter signal epoch is captured, leading to a coarser frequency resolution. For instance, the TD receiver implementation described in [16] in connection with oscilloscope PicoScope PS5444B from Pico Technologies (200 MHz bandwidth, max. sampling rate 1 GSa/s) chooses the sampling rate 62.5 MSa/s and 30 ms epoch ($N = 1.875 \text{ MSa}$) in CISPR bands A/B with theoretical frequency resolution $\Delta f = 33.33 \text{ Hz}$. In practice, it is resampled to achieve $\Delta f = 50 \text{ Hz}$ (RBW/4) as shown in Fig. 4, which is quite coarse compared to the CISPR band A filter bandwidth (200 Hz). To obtain finer frequency resolution, data interpolation must be implemented in the receiver software (which does not correspond to the actual hardware capabilities).

Fig. 4. Frequency tuning accuracy measurement.

C. Response to Pulses

According to [3], the absolute and relative pulse response for all the weighting detectors shall be evaluated. The requirement of [3] Annex B is the following:

The response of a measuring receiver to pulses having an impulse area of $0.022 \mu\text{Vs}$, having a uniform spectrum up to at least 1000 MHz, repeated at a frequency of 100 Hz, shall for all frequencies of tuning, be equal to the response to an unmodulated sine-wave signal at the tuned frequency having an rms value of 1 mV ($60 \text{ dB}(\mu\text{V})$). The impulse area produced

by the generator shall be known with an error not greater than ± 0.5 dB. The pulse repetition frequency shall be known with an error not greater than 1 %.

As discussed earlier, currently, the only solution for the calibration is either using a nanosecond pulse generator or a pulse-modulated CW signal. Historically, there has been confusion about the terminology used with the pulse generator characterization, see, e.g. [17]. One can find terms spectrum amplitude, impulse area, spectral intensity or spectral density in the literature, whereas the most common is the use of spectrum amplitude (ideal rectangular pulse) and impulse area (general pulse shape). All quantities for the characterization of pulse generators have dimensional units V/Hz or the mathematical equivalent. The (base-band) pulse generator produces in the ideal case pulses with amplitude A and duration T . The frequency-dependent spectrum amplitude is then calculated as

$$S(f) = 2AT \left| \frac{\sin(\pi fT)}{\pi fT} \right|. \quad (2)$$

The shorter the pulse duration T , the higher the frequency of the first null in the spectrum and, thus, the higher the frequency up to which the spectrum is considered uniform. The spectrum of repetitive pulses is discrete, with the distance between lines inversely proportional to the pulse repetition rate. The pulse generator output does not have an ideal rectangular shape and its spectrum decays faster. The required impulse area for each CISPR band is shown in Table I.

TABLE I
STANDARD IMPULSE AREA SPECIFICATIONS (OPEN CIRCUIT).

Frequency Band	Impulse Area (μ Vs)
A	13.5
B	0.316
C	0.044
D	0.044

Another option is to use a pulse-modulated CW signal (radiofrequency pulse). The spectrum is uniform in a given bandwidth, whereas pulses with longer duration can be used with lower amplitudes than base-band pulse generators. Assuming the ideal rectangular shape of the modulating signal the spectral amplitude is determined as

$$S(f) = AT \left| \frac{\sin(\pi fT)}{\pi fT} - \frac{\sin[\pi(2f_c + \Delta f)T]}{\pi(2f_c + \Delta f)T} \right|, \quad (3)$$

where $\Delta f = f - f_c$, f is the CW carrier frequency, A is the peak signal amplitude and T is the pulse duration. The spectrum is not entirely symmetrical, however, in a narrow band around the carrier frequency and for a sufficient number of CW periods in the pulse (>15) the asymmetry is negligible [18]. The energy of the pulse is concentrated around the f_c which makes the radiofrequency pulse the only usable solution for receivers without preselection. The use of a synthesized trapezoidal waveform or a multisine waveform in CISPR bands A, B was described in [15].

Generally, the response of particular detectors to a pulse signal is $PK > QP > RMS > AV$. There are several methods for the characterization of nanosecond pulse generators and pulse-modulated RF generators given in [3] Annex C. However, only a very brief description of the methods is given and technical details are hidden. In [17], the main calibration methods of base-band pulse generators were compared together with the achievable measurement uncertainty (i.e. the Fourier transform of a time-domain pulse waveform, the intermediate-frequency measurement method, the measurement of pulse amplitude and duration and the measurement of one spectrum line amplitude). The measurement uncertainty of the pulse generator characterization at the primary level (i.e. traceable to SI units) is also discussed in e.g. [19]. The impulse area of a pulse generator determined by one of the methods discussed in [17] is then used as a reference value for the calibration of pulse-modulated CW signals. In the past, there were various nanosecond pulse generators available in the market (e.g. Picosecond Pulse Labs 1000D, Hewlett Packard HP 8082A, EMG Type 11590 (TR-0307)). Nowadays de facto the only supplier of these generators is Schwarzbeck, Germany (e.g. model IGUU 2916).

The calibration of the response to pulses of heterodyne EMI receivers or real-time EMI receivers with preselection filters is well established and it is quite fast because these receivers can be quickly tuned to the desired frequency. In practice, one to three carrier frequencies are chosen in each CISPR band A to D. In the case of direct sampling TD receivers, one has to acquire a large number of waveform samples to obtain the full spectrum in a particular CISPR band, therefore processing time might be significant. For instance, the implementation by [16] with oscilloscope PicoScope PS5444B uses a sample rate 62.5 MSa/s for band A, where pulse-modulated CW signal with carrier frequency 100 kHz and pulse repetition rate 60 Hz was acquired (arbitrary waveform generator Agilent 33120A). 37.5 million samples were taken with sampling period $T_s = 16$ ns, which corresponds to an epoch of length 600 ms (37 pulse bursts). QP detector was chosen in the said receiver software.

Fig. 5. Pulse-modulated CW signal (detail of one burst in the inset).

After performing FFT, there are spurious products in the

spectrum due to oscilloscope non-idealities (A/D clock, not perfectly uniform sampling due to free-running oscillator independent of the signal generator, noise). After limiting the spectrum to band A (9 kHz - 150 kHz) and applying numerical RBW=200 Hz, one gets the response of the QP detector in Fig. 6. For pulse repetition frequencies 2 Hz, 1 Hz or single pulse, only one burst is usually present in the whole captured time waveform and the measurement is lengthy.

Fig. 6. Spectrum of the pulse-modulated sine wave, $f_c = 100$ kHz, repetition rate 60 Hz, CISPR band A.

D. Weighting Detectors (Selectivity)

IF filters of spectrum analyzers are usually defined by their 3 dB bandwidth, which is suitable for measuring CW signals. When measuring broadband signals using EMI receivers the single bandwidth specification for the IF filter is insufficient since the filter's amplitude and phase response will affect the measurement. Instead of a single figure of merit for each CISPR band (i.e. 6 dB bandwidth of 200 Hz for band A, 9 kHz for band B, 120 kHz for bands C/D), the standard [3] defines tolerance masks for the selectivity together with their margin (the tolerance is relatively high, which may originate from old analogue filters that were not so precise as modern digital filters). Generally, many different digital filter windows are compliant with the overall pass-band selectivity and thus e.g. different emissions spectra can be obtained for the same scenario using receivers with different filter implementations. A study of differences between various digital EMI receivers (all of them CISPR 16-1-1 compliant) is given e.g. in [20]. Due to the nature of impulse signals, some of the spectral components are outside of the IF filter passband at any one time.

For heterodyne or real-time FFT spectrum analyzers, the spectral mask of IF filters in CISPR bands A to D is determined using a calibrated power meter and CW generator. The reading of the receiver is recorded, then the power level of the generator is reduced by a small step (e.g. 0.1 dB) and the delta marker in the receiver is recorded. The frequency of the CW generator is then changed and the analyzer's delta marker reading 0 dB is observed. In this way, the whole selectivity curve is measured with metrological traceability. Then usually the 6 dB bandwidth is

determined in the same way as with spectrum analyzers because this may be of interest to users of the receiver. An important measurement uncertainty component is the slope of the curve, which is determined by measuring power and frequency values in the vicinity of the 6 dB drop, see Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Measurement of 6 dB nominal bandwidth of IF filters.

Time-domain EMI receivers measure the whole selectivity curve in one step by performing FFT of the input CW signal. The accuracy of determination of the selectivity curve depends on the frequency resolution (inversely proportional to the total acquired epoch length) and usually for practical reasons of measurement speed this resolution is rather coarse. Fig. 8 shows an example of measurement of the band B filter (nominal 9 kHz bandwidth for 6 dB drop) with $\Delta f = 2.25$ kHz, similar figure can be shown for the band A filter (nominal 200 Hz bandwidth for 6 dB drop) with $\Delta f = 50$ Hz. It can be seen that both the selectivity curve and the 6 dB bandwidth are determined with measurement uncertainty larger than with frequency-swept receivers due to coarse frequency resolution and consequently roughly estimated curve slope. The frequency resolution can be artificially increased by interpolation (as in the implementation by [16] in connection with oscilloscope PicoScope PS5444B; different TD receivers may have different software and thus the accuracy of determining the selectivity filters can be different).

Fig. 8. Example of measurement of filter selectivity, $f_c = 15$ MHz, sample rate 62.5 MSa/s, time epoch 30 ms, $\Delta f = 2.25$ kHz.

For CISPR band E (1 GHz to 18 GHz), the impulse bandwidth of 1 MHz is defined which is measured differently from the tolerance mask. The impulse bandwidth as

$$B_{imp} = \frac{V_p}{D}, \quad (4)$$

where V_p is the RMS voltage of the detected transient and D is the spectral density (in RMS volts) of the impulse signal causing the transient. Standard [3] Annex E defines three methods to measure this parameter. Due to problems with precise characterization of the spectral density, a method is widely used which employs a pulse signal with different pulse repetition frequencies (works for both nanosecond pulse generators and pulse-modulated CW generators). In the first step the pulse repetition frequency f_{R1} is set to a value much higher than the resolution bandwidth of the receiver (only one spectral component falls within the filter bandwidth), in the second case f_{R2} is much lower than the filter bandwidth (many spectrum lines fall within the filter bandwidth). After tuning the receiver to the pulse repetition frequency, the impulse bandwidth is determined as

$$B_{imp} = f_{R1} \frac{V_p}{V_2}, \quad (5)$$

where V_p and V_2 are measured voltages for two different repetition frequencies, respectively. The choice of repetition frequencies is sometimes limited to the available settings of the pulse generator. For more details see [3] Annex E. The measurement of impulse bandwidth is relatively easy using frequency-swept receivers as they can be quickly tuned to any frequency. The TD receivers must capture very long signal epochs to satisfy sufficient frequency resolution and thus the measurement speed is lower and the calibration is more cumbersome compared to frequency-swept receivers.

IV. CONCLUSION

The use of TD measuring receivers is popular and advantageous for many EMC testing scenarios. Tests that require large frequency spans can be performed by several orders quicker than using traditional frequency-swept EMI receivers. They also allow multichannel operation, i.e. several disturbance sources can be measured in parallel and their correlation can be studied. On the other hand, the TD measuring receivers are more complicated in terms of their calibration and metrological characterization. Tests which are quick and easy with frequency-swept receivers (filter selectivity, response to pulses) are rather slow and cumbersome with TD receivers. One problem is the poor support of current CISPR 16-1-1 with regard to characterization methods of TD measuring receivers, the other problem is the variety of custom EMI software solutions that are often friendly for the EMC testing users, but less friendly to metrology calibration laboratories (often access to internal software constants is needed to check the manufacturer's specifications and conformance with CISPR 16-1-1 correctly). Close cooperation with a manufacturer of such a receiver is then required.

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